

A Practical Approach to Uncertainty and Validation of Process Simulation for LCM Manufacture

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Background

- In the manufacture of composites by liquid composite moulding (LCM), a liquid resin is infused through a textile reinforcement within a mould that provides the shape and thickness of the component being made. To ensure the efficient and complete saturation of the reinforcement, simulation can be used as part of the design of the manufacturing process.
- One of the key data inputs used in the simulation of the manufacturing process is the permeability of the reinforcement, K . Here, Darcy's Law is applied to measure how well a fluid will flow through the reinforcement. Following several decades of study and interlaboratory trials, a standardised method for the experimental measurement of the in-plane permeability is available (ISO 4410:2023).
- While extensive research has been carried out into both the determination of permeability and simulation of manufacture, industry uptake of these tools remains low due to lack of familiarity and confidence in the application and resulting data.

The in-plane permeability can be measured by injecting a model fluid into a dry textile specimen and monitoring the flow front progression with respect to time. The major and minor permeability values (K_1 and K_2) are then calculated using Darcy's Law:

$$v = -\frac{K}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta L}$$

K = permeability (m^2); ΔP = pressure drop; ΔL = flow length; v = flow velocity; η = fluid viscosity

Objectives

- The work presented here was carried out with the aims of bringing together the knowledge of how to simulate the manufacture of a composite part via LCM, and the experimental measurement of permeability as one of the major data inputs for simulation.
- The final goal is to increase industry use of these tools, in support of the development of manufacturing processes that are time and cost efficient and result in high quality parts.
- The work will test the robustness of these tools and provide an assessment of the expected level of accuracy of the process from characterisation through to simulation, in order to build more trust in the data outputs and enhance their useability.
- The work will provide an understanding of the main contributors to uncertainty, and how these can be mitigated or managed.
- The final outcomes will provide a source of open access information that can be used by anyone to understand the tools, where a lot of previous knowledge has been commercially protected.

Preliminary case study: flat panel

- An initial case study was carried out as an initial proof of concept of how the accuracy of the permeability can influence the result of the simulation and the basis of the next phase of work.
- An FE model of the NPL RTM tool was created using Abaqus CAE. The filling of the tool was simulated using LIMS. Permeability values used in the simulation were taken from values experimentally measured following the standard test procedure described in ISO 4410:2023 and supporting research. [1][2]
- An interlaboratory comparison exercise, carried out as the precursor to ISO 4410:2023, showed that data between sites can vary as much as 40%. To assess the impact of this level of uncertainty, the simulation was rerun using permeability data 40% higher and lower than the experimentally obtained values. The results are summarised in Table 1.
- The comparison of the simulated to the experimental values is given in Table 2.

Table 1. Effect of permeability variation on simulated fill time

	Kxx (m ²)	Kyy (m ²)	Fill time (min:s)
Original	2.3e-11	4.24e-12	19:47
Higher	2.76e-11	5.088e-12	16:29
Lower	1.84e-11	3.392e-12	24:43

Table 2. Comparison of simulated to experimental fill times

Simulated	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3
19:47	12:35	12:50	11:00

Second case study: complex shape

- Following the preliminary work, a second case study was carried out following the same steps of (1) measure the permeability; (2) simulate the mould filling and (3) compare the simulation to experimental values.
- In this second case study, a more complex shape was used. Here, the experimental work and simulations were carried out on a double-dome shape (Fig. 5). This shape is commonly used in the study of composites manufacture as it allows for the examination of the effects of a number of different geometrical features.
- Here, as the fabric is now draped over a 3D shape, the draping results in different areas of shear. The shearing of the fabric is known to change the permeability in localised areas, where opening up of the tows provides for easier flow and a higher permeability.
- The effect of simulating the mould filling using locally different permeability values was studied by first measuring the permeability of specimens that had undergone controlled degrees of shear, with the aim of applying these to the model for increased accuracy.

Fig. 5. Double dome mould

Sheared permeability measurement

- The permeability of sheared specimens was measured using a specially designed frame as shown in Fig. 6. Here, the specimens were clamped along two parallel edges of the frame. The frame was able to move in a scissor movement, allowing for a pure shear condition.
- Specimens were made from 3 layers of fabric and tested at a cavity height of 0.7 mm to provide a fibre volume fraction of 0.5. The number of layers used here reflected the setup used in the double-dome mould experiments. This is fewer layers than would typically be used in an in-plane permeability measurement, however keeping the number of layers low provided the additional benefit of minimising any differences in shear angle between each layer.
- The frame was used with the top part of NPL's radial permeameter.
- Flow front data was processed using NPL's flow front detection algorithm, which tracks the elliptical flow front and automatically calculates the in-plane permeability.

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram of shear frame

Sheared permeability test results

- As seen in the example in Fig. 7, the shearing of the fabric resulted in a flow front that was not perfectly elliptical. It should be noted that the algorithm used to calculate the permeability continuously fits the moving flow front to a perfect ellipse, which resulted in a reduced applicability here. At present, radial permeability measurement is always based on an assumed elliptical flow, so this remains the most current solution available.
- The permeability values were plotted against the known angle of shear of the specimens and plotted against the fit established in previous works. As seen in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, the data showed a reasonable fit to the expected trend.

Fig. 7. Example flow through sheared specimen

Fig. 8. k_1 values against shear angle

Fig. 9. k_2 values against shear angle

Simulation of the mould filling

- Flow through the mould was simulated using uniform permeability values taken from measurements carried out following the standard method, i.e. a flat and unsheared specimen (Fig. 11)
- The drape of the fabric over the mould was then modelled (Fig. 10) to obtain the localised shear angle of the fabric at different parts of the model component. This was used to apply localised permeability values taken from the sheared specimen tests. The flow was then modelled as shown in Fig. 12. Here we can see the change in predicted flow front.

Fig. 10. Model of fabric drape in mould

Fig. 11. Simulated mould filling using uniform permeability values

Fig. 12. Simulated mould filling using non-uniform permeability values

Infusion into the double-dome mould

- Laboratory-scale infusions were carried out using the double-dome mould at the University of Nottingham. The fabric was the same Hexcel 2/2 twill woven fabric as characterised in the permeability measurements and engine oil was used as a model fluid. Injections were carried out at 0.1 MPa
- Using video footage of the experiments, the movement of the flow front was tracked using NPL's automated system. These data were used to generate colour maps of the flow front progression
- The scale of the colour map was programmed to produce clear and readable isolines. An example output is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Generation of colour maps of flow front progression

Time-stamping the flow front progression

- In order to be able to compare the experimental values to simulated data it was necessary to time stamp the images using a means that would be comparable to the simulation. Homography transformation (projective transformation) was used to align the video images to the simulated images, using the inlet and vent holes as the reference.
- Markers were placed on the cardinal axes at the time bounds of the simulated images to enable comparison with the flow arrival time from the experimental measurements (Fig 14). A representative graph is given in Fig. 15 of the progression of the flow from the experimental data. For increased accuracy, in further work these points will be taken from the mesh of the simulation in order to assign a scale to the distance markers. The next step will be to fine tune the simulation for comparison to these experimental data.

Fig. 14. Cardinal axes

Fig. 15. Flow front progression

Accuracy of permeability

- In order to ensure the most accurate simulation, the permeability input data need to be precise. As shown in the preliminary case study, changes in the permeability input data can have a significant impact on the simulation of even a simple shape. Throughout this work, a number of areas of improvement have been identified for further development, including:
 - The low number of layers used in the measurement of the permeability of sheared specimens was beneficial in ensuring that any difference in the degree of shear between the layers was minimised, however this may affect accuracy of permeability measurement in other ways such as increased impact of surface effects of the tool on the volume fraction, e.g. parallelism of the top and bottom plates and any features of the tool such as sensor placement.
 - The compliance correction required for cavity height settings was proportionally quite high – 0.2 mm correction for a 0.7 mm thickness setting. Ensuring the correction is carried out is essential to accurate reporting of the volume fraction.
 - It was noted that care was required during loading and unloading of specimens with respect to any fluid remaining in the system. If fluid remained, it would leak prematurely onto the specimen, prior to the start of the controlled injection and potentially contain bubbles. Therefore, the best course of action was to begin each test with an emptied inlet tube.
 - The tool used to measure the sheared specimen permeability had been significantly modified from the method used to measure the permeability following the standard method, effectively resulting in what could be considered a “different” tool. Interlaboratory trials have shown variability between different tools which can significantly impact mould filling simulations.
 - Benchmarking trials using nominally the same fabric have shown that there is batch to batch variability in the architecture at scales relevant to permeability measurement. Different values were measured on different batches of the “same” fabric. [3][4]

Uncertainty of measurement

- In order to further understand the accuracy of the permeability measurements, measurement uncertainty evaluation was performed by identifying and quantifying the sources:

- Injection pressure
- Fluid viscosity
- Radius of injection port
- Volume fraction
- Flow front position
- Time

Fig. 16. Histogram showing measurement uncertainty

- Using Monte Carlo simulation, it was possible to quantify the uncertainty for each measurement at 95% CI at 11% for K_1 and 12% for K_2 (Fig. 16).

Proposed next steps and concluding remarks

- The two case studies presented here show a preliminary effort to assess the accuracy of mould filling simulations and the impact of permeability values as an input parameter.
- The permeability of sheared specimens was successfully measured, and the influence of mapping a non-uniform permeability onto simulations of the mould filling vs using a uniform value was shown.
- In the next steps, following refinements to the simulations, these results will be put together to form a complete picture and provide an accessible understanding of the process of characterising textile reinforcements and simulating the manufacture of a composite part.
- Here, some of the complexity of this process has been shown, highlighting the importance of putting these methods through their paces at all stages from fabric characterisation through to simulation and manufacture.
- Ongoing work is being carried out into the virtual characterisation of permeability, which may pave the way for a suitable alternative to experimental measurements [ref].

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Further information on this work is available at: <https://eprintspublications.npl.co.uk/>

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